

Social Entrepreneurs: Need of the Moment for Changing the Face of the Society in India

Md Nasim Ansari,

UGC Junior Research Fellow, Department of Commerce,
University of North Bengal, Siliguri, West Bengal;

Monica Mahali,

UGC Junior Research Fellow, Department of Commerce,
Vidyasagar University, Medinipur, West Bengal;

Abstract:- Social entrepreneurship in India has one of the most diverse ecosystems, with numerous opportunities. In the fields of education, healthcare, poverty eradication, sanitation, agriculture, waste management, renewable energy, manufacturing, skill development, etc., there are numerous opportunities to collaborate with local partners and implement innovative solutions and succeed in these sectors by putting in a collective effort and delivering innovative solutions to the table to India's numerous social challenges. However, for social entrepreneurs to be agile and sustain in the face of adversity, the enterprise, its stakeholders, and the government all must work collectively to address the numerous challenges confronting these sectors, keeping in mind these enterprises that are at the forefront of bringing about real and positive social changes in society. The present study focuses on understanding the concepts, need, importance, scope, and as well as issues and challenges that Social Entrepreneurs face in India.

Keywords:- Social Entrepreneurs, Diverse ecosystem, Opportunities, Social challenges, Need).

I. INTRODUCTION

Social entrepreneurship is an activity in which individuals, start-up, and entrepreneurs evolve and provide solutions for social, environmental, and cultural issues. Their ultimate goal is directly tied to creating social value with little or no intention to gain personal profit. Traditionally, entrepreneurship has been linked with an organization that aims for high profit giving tough competition to their competitors. There is a big difference between a social entrepreneur and a business entrepreneur. Social Entrepreneurs are Peoples who recognize an opportunity to meet unmet social needs need that the nation's welfare system will not or cannot meet, and collect the necessary resources (generally people, money, premises, and often volunteers) and use them to make a difference (Thompson 2000). Social entrepreneurship is a for-profit business model that acts as a change-maker in the society who in turn affect others to contribute toward the growth and development of the society, community, or the world. According to Bill Drayton (founder of Ashoka Foundation) as the originator of social entrepreneurship, there are two key characteristics of social entrepreneurship- first, social innovation has the potential to reshape society's existing system. Second, the presence of a visionary, creative, entrepreneurial individual, as well as the ethics that underpin the innovative idea. Despite the obstacles or constraints that it faces, a social entrepreneur is deeply engaged in the integration of learning, transformation, advancement, and continuous

action, and bears the responsibility to the community for the results achieved.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Citizens' democratic values as members of society are shaped in large part by socialpreneur. A socialpreneur makes a positive contribution to civic virtue. Civic virtue is a sense of understanding and knowledge that emerges from within us to participate in developing nations and make a significant contribution to the progress of the country without being coerced by anyone. (Ramadhanty & D Ramdan, 2019). Social entrepreneurs are concerned with societal economic, social, and environmental issues that are of, for, and about society. They are driven to shift the unfavorable balance; they sympathize with disgruntled people looking for ways to improve things and find the best solutions. Because of their diverse cultural backgrounds, work areas, and issues they are attempting to solve, each social entrepreneur is unique (S. Shukla, S. Shukla & Vikash Singh, 2016). Social entrepreneurship creates innovative solutions to immediate social problems while also mobilizing the thoughts, abilities, resources, and social conditions necessary for long-term change (Alvord, Brown & Letts, 2004). The social entrepreneur is someone who detects an unfortunate but stable equilibrium that causes deprivation, marginalization, or adversity for a segment of society; who applies his or her motivation, innovation, direct courage, action, and fortitude to this condition; and who strives for and significantly influences the formation of stable equilibrium that preserves long-term benefit for the specific group and the general public (Martin & Osberg, 2007). Social entrepreneurship benefits those at the bottom of the economic pyramid. Social entrepreneurs must be creative, socially conscious, and willing to take risks. Communication of the business idea, obtaining skilled workers, obtaining funds, working remotely, obtaining government approval, acquiring technologies, raising awareness, and competing with others are just a few of the challenges that social entrepreneurs face (B Sivathanu & P V Bhise, 2013). In Latvia, the growth of social enterprises is very slow due to a lack of a legal framework, a lack of public understanding and knowledge about social entrepreneurship, insufficient financial support from state and local governments, and a lack of adequate education and practice for social entrepreneurs, (Bikse, Rivza & Riemere, 2014).

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the Concept and Need for social entrepreneurship in India.
- To ascertain the importance and role of social entrepreneurship in India.
- To know the scope, opportunities, and challenges of social entrepreneurship in India.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on secondary data. The sources for the data collection are research papers, articles, books, and related websites.

V. SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

An entrepreneur is characterized by the personal risk they take in pursuit of a new business, invention, or another kind of entrepreneurship. In exchange for taking that risk, they frequently benefit the most from the success of their business. Thus, the Professional application of knowledge, skills, and abilities, as well as the monetization of a new

concept, by an individual or a group of people by founding a firm, to pursue growth while creating money, employment, and social good is called an entrepreneur (Prem S. Potabatti, Nikhil D. Boob, 2015) The concept of innovation in the theory of entrepreneurship has been introduced by the Schumpeter (Schumpeter, J.A. 1934). An entrepreneur can be defined as one who maximizes opportunity at right the time with a profit motive (Drucker, P.F. 2006). A social entrepreneur is someone who turns unique ideas into applications with the potential to alleviate community-based challenges. These people are prepared to take the risk and put out the effort to effect positive social change through their efforts. Social entrepreneurship is all about identifying social problems and effecting social change by the use of entrepreneurial concepts, processes, and operations. It is all about conducting research to fully describe a specific social problem and then organizing, establishing, and managing a social initiative to achieve the desired change. The reform may or may not entail the complete eradication of a societal issue. It might be a life-long effort aimed at improving the current situation.

• Social Entrepreneur:

Fig. 1

Source: Author

VI. IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

Social entrepreneurs enhance people's lives by championing critical projects that do not originally have a profit motive, even if these endeavors subsequently provide economic rewards. India's most of the social problems are chronic in nature and they cannot be solved through the traditional approach, thus it needs some unusual modern solution. This is where India feels the importance of social entrepreneurs as they come up with modern, unusual, and unique ideas with the motive of creating social good. Some of India's chronic social problems that make social entrepreneurship even more important are hunger, poverty, unemployment, clean water, sanitation, gender inequality and quality and affordable education, etc. Table 1, 2, 3, and 4 shows India's current standings all over the world. Hence, Social Entrepreneurs could really be a gamechanger for India as it:

- Highlights the existing problem (Either Chronic or New)

- Provides Economic Values to the society (Jobs and Employment)
- The catalyst for social change
- Creator of unique opportunities
- Promotes Equity in the society
- Acts as an Inspiration
- Promotes Corporate Social Responsibilities
- Uses unutilized resources for the benefit of the society

VII. SCOPE AND OPPORTUNITIES OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

The development and prosperity of any nation can be seen by its Gross Domestic Product (GDP), per capita income, unemployment rate, poverty rate, literacy rate, gender equality, healthcare system, etc. Social entrepreneurs could play a pivotal role in the growth of a nation if the infusion is to make societal change. The scope for social entrepreneurship in India is huge as the nation is still young in growth. The areas where India faces a problem, and there are numerous opportunities for social entrepreneurs are:

Fig. 2

Source: Author

VIII. WHY DOES INDIA NEED SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP?

India, being a developing economy, needs a large number of social entrepreneurs today. People from all walks of life are needed to spark a revolution in developing and implementing effective, innovative, and long-term solutions to social and environmental concerns. These solutions include both for-profit and non-profit services and goods.

India requires a large number of social entrepreneurs who can provide creative solutions to society's most important social problems, such as unemployment, poverty, sanitation, education, water and waste management, gender inequality, primary health care, carbon emissions, and other environmental issues. Tables Showing Some indexes where India Stands:

Urban	Rural	India
8.5%	7.2%	7.6%

Table 1: Unemployment Rate (April 2022*)

Source: <https://unemploymentinindia.cmie.com>. * 30-day Moving Average

Male (M)	Female (F)	India	Gap (M-F)
82.14%	65.46%	74.04%	16.68%

Table 2: Literacy Rate (Census 2021)

Source: <https://censusofindia2021.com>

Rural	Urban	National	Source
32.75%	8.81%	25.01%	NITI Aayog

Table 3: Poverty Rate in India During 2015-16

Source: NITI Aayog

Name of the Indexes	Ranking/Countries	Source
Global Health Security Index (GHS)	66th/195	www.ghsindex.org
Global Hunger Index (GHI)	101th/116	www.globalhungerindex.org
Human Development Index (HDI)	131th/189	www.hdr.undp.org
Global Gender Gap Report	140 th /156	www.pib.gov.in
Environmental Performance Index	168 th /180 (2020)	www.nationalheraldindia.com
Global Multi DimensionPoverty Index (MPI)	66 th /109	www.hdr.undp.org
World Happiness Index	136 th /146 (2022)	www.dmerharyana.org
Ease of Doing Business	66 th /190 (2020)	www.makeinindia.com

Table 4: Rankings of India in different Social Parameters (2021)

The tables are showing true pictures of our country. India needs to improve these indexes through continuous efforts. Social entrepreneurs have huge opportunities to improve these areas with proper collaboration with the govt. and the public as they drive social transformation and bring a positive change in the world. Indexes are showing the areas where India lags behind the developing world and hence needs an urgent call for Entrepreneurs as well as Social Entrepreneurs.

IX. CHALLENGES OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Social entrepreneurs have a significant influence on communities and social relationships. When establishing socially responsible companies, it is critical to understand their problems. India needs social entrepreneurs at the moment to overcome several social problems.

Social entrepreneurs in India are facing several challenges to grow or establish an industry for the social cause, these challenges are:

- Lack of funding support
- Finding the right people to go further with
- Lack of proper management after reaching an inflection point
- Lack of proper strategy and ability to scale up
- Making balance between Vision and Business
- Standing true to the vision
- Resistance by the people to accept the change
- Creating awareness
- Delays in Government approval

X. WHAT WILL MAKE A SOCIAL ENTREPRENEUR SUCCESSFUL IN INDIA?

The study shows the need for social entrepreneurs in India for the development of different parameters. Becoming a social entrepreneur is never going to be an easy task, hence it needs external support either from the government or from the public (Vendor, p., et al.2012). Social entrepreneurs require a higher level of resilience and perseverance says the CEO of GiveIndia. Some secrets which can make a social entrepreneur successful are-

- Solving the most important problem instead of a lucrative one.
- Collaboration with the government and with other social entrepreneurs
- Tracking the success
- Learning to sustain long
- Making employees understand the mission and vision
- Stand true to the vision
- Creating networks to increase outreach and scale
- Making start-up-friendly Environment

XI. CONCLUSION

Social entrepreneurship has the potential to transform the face of society in India; there have been several examples and initiatives that have run under the umbrella of social entrepreneurship and have proven to be life-changing for individuals in the surrounding area. Societal

entrepreneurship, in particular, has brighter potential in India, where social concerns are in full swing. The study shows the scope and opportunities, importance, and need of social entrepreneurs in India where India's standings in the world index have been tabulated. If the government and other stakeholders can properly address the issues of social entrepreneurship, then social entrepreneurship is without a doubt the most crucial weapon with the potential to transform the very face of society in India.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Alvord, S. H., Brown, L. D., & Letts, C. W. (2004). Social entrepreneurship and societal transformation: An exploratory study. *The journal of applied behavioral science*, 40(3), 260-282.
- [2.] Bikse, V., Rivza, B., & Riemere, I. (2015). The social entrepreneur as a promoter of social advancement. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 185, 469-478. Bulsara, H. P., Gandhi, S., & Chandwani, J. (2015). Social entrepreneurship in India: An exploratory study. *International Journal of Innovation*, 3(1), 7-16.
- [3.] Drucker, P. F. (2006). *Innovation and Entrepreneurship: Practice and principles* (Reprint). New York, NY: HarperBusiness.
- [4.] Martin, R. L. and Osberg, S. (2007). Social entrepreneurship: The case for definition. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, Vol.5, Issue 2, pp28-39.
- [5.] Potabatti, P. S., & Boob, N. D. (2015). Youth entrepreneurship: Opportunities and challenges in India. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 5(2), 55-59.
- [6.] Ramadhanty, W. G., & Ramdan, D. (2019, August). SOCIALPRENEUR: BUILDING THE CIVILIZATION OF THE EMPIRE. In *International Conference of One Asia Community* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 13-16).
- [7.] Schumpeter, J., & Opie, R. (1934). *The theory of economic development*. Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press.
- [8.] Shukla, S., Shukla, S., & Singh, V. (2016). Social entrepreneurship: A concept towards societal improvement. *Journal of IPEM*, 10(2), 38-46.
- [9.] Sivathanu, B., & Bhise, P. V. (2013). Challenges for social entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAEM)*, 9-10.
- [10.] Yaduvanshi, J., & Narendran, R. (2017). Social entrepreneurship in India: Opportunities and challenges. *Commonwealth Journal of Commerce & Management Research*, 4(2).
- [11.] Thompson, J., Alvy, G. and Lees, A. (2000), "Social entrepreneurship – a new look at the people and the potential", *Management Decision*, Vol. 38 No. 5, pp. 328-338. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00251740010340517>